

STUDYING OF ELBEK'S CREATION

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Abstract. This article gives us about one of the prominent of Jadid literature called Mashrikh Yunusov (Elbek)'s complex life and undying creature. In the main part, an opinion is expressed about the history of the study of the literary heritage of the creator, and the works of such scholars as Nurmuhhammad Kabulov, Ortikhboy Abdullayev, Haydarali Uzokov and Ulughmurad Amonov are disclosed. Aspects of Elbek's work applied by these scientists are considered and a reaction is expressed.

Keywords: Elbek, creativity, the history of learning, enlightenment, liberty, press.

In the 20s and 30s of the 20th century, many enlightened people entered the field of Turkestan literature and press. One of them is Elbek, who actively participated in the field of new Uzbek enlightenment and culture. Elbek is a well-known poet, writer, journalist, folklorist, linguist and famous pedagogue, who worked effectively in the 20s and 30s. His real name is Mashrikh Yunusov, and Elbek is his nickname. Mashrikh Yunusov was born 125 years ago - in 1898 in the village of Khumson in the Bostonlikh district of Tashkent in the family of Yunus.

His literary work began in 1917, and his first poems were published in the newspapers "El bayrog'i" ("El Bayroghi"), "Turon" ("Turon"), "Turk so'zi" ("Turk sozi"), "Ulug' Turkiston" ("Ulugh Turkistan"), as well as "O'zbek yosh shoirlar to'plami" ("Uzbek Young Poets Collection") was printed. The author who is Elbek's "Armug'on", ("Armugon"), "Yolqinlar" ("Lights"), "Sezgililar" ("Feelings"), "Mehnat kuylari" ("Work tunes"), "G'unchalar" ("Buds"), "Chirchiq bo'ylarida" ("Besides Chirchik"), "Bolalar qo'shig'i" ("Children's song"), "She'rlar to'plami" ("Collection of poems"), "She'rlar" ("Poems") poetry collections such as "Anorgul" ("Anorgul"), "Go'zal qiz" ("Beautiful Girl"), "Turkiston" ("Turkistan"), "Bizniki" ("Ours"), "Paxta" ("Cotton"), "O'tmishim" ("My Past"), "Chirchiq" ("Chirchik"), "Batrak kolxozi" ("Batrak collective farm"), "O'zbekiston" ("Uzbekistan"), "Bog'bon" ("Gardener"), "Etik" ("Boot"), "Rifleman" ("Mergan") epics, poetic novel "Tozagul" ("Tozagul"), "Qo'shchi Turg'un" ("Koshchi Turghun"), "Dadamat" ("Dadamat") is the author.

In Elbek's poetic and prose works, the description of events taken from the recent history of the Uzbek people, including the poet's past, occupies an important place. After all, the opinions of professor Abdurahman Sa'di, an accomplished critic and literary critic, are a clear proof of this: "Elbek started parable-making in the Uzbek literature of the later period. He took the path of giving birth to parables, not through translation. No one else has been seen on this road yet" (Qabulov N. 1988, p. 42). Ashurali Zahiri said, "The poet Elbek was a great artist who made use of the understandable influences of the national language in taking oral literature from the people and re-delivering it to the people, creating parables in children's literature" (Uzokov H. 1999, p. 9) - described as. Elbek's life and works have been studied by a number of literary scholars, linguists and historians. By studying the work of the poet, they proved that Elbek is a prolific artist.

In particular, the study of the rebellious poet's work began in the 70s and 80s of the last century, and after independence, his legacy began to be collected intensively. Nurmuhhammad Qabulov, Ortiqboy Abdullayev, Haydarali Uzokov, Ulug'murad Amonov, Shaira Bobomurodova among literary critics, linguists and historians studied and published his work.

Literary critic Nurmuhhammad Qabulov, in his critical-biographical essay published in 1988, describes his research on Elbek's life and work. Although this book contains many controversial points, it can provide valuable information about Elbeck's prolific work. At first, he critically approaches the poet's work in his work: "In the early years of his work, he cannot express the era in full images, there is hopelessness", (Qabulov N. 1988, p. 6) he evaluates and gives examples of a number of his poems citing that they did not have a clear goal and position. He analyzes the poet's poems on a number of topics and expresses his opinion on them. Of course, it is necessary to remember that the author may have approached it from the point of view of the period. The author, who initially approached in a critical spirit, later says that good changes began to appear in Elbek's work and he strengthened his ideological position. For example, citing the poem "Mening hikoyam" ("My Story") as an example, he emphasizes that the purpose of the poet is clear in it, and Elbek says that "writing poetry is not a hobby for me". At this point, it is appropriate to remember that our poet modestly said, "I have not yet written a single poem, but I have not turned back from the path of poetry" (Qabulov N. 1988, p. 9). In addition, he emphasizes that poetry prevails over storytelling in the artist, and says that he has often referred to the image of the sun in his work and that it has become an expression of the

new era. As an example, it shows the artist's poems such as "Bahor" and "Sun".

Professor and historian Haydarali Uzokov's work dedicated to the study of Elbek's work is noteworthy. He studied the creative heritage of the poet, collected them and worked effectively to convey them to the people. As a result, he discovered several unknown works by Elbek and compiled them, publishing the poet's Selected Works in 1999. In his preface, he describes the poet as "a selfless devotee who went on the path of love" (Uzokov H. 1999, p. 5). The professor noted that more than 30 separately published books of the poet, more than a thousand poems, epics, ballads, folk songs, stories, essays, scientific-methodological articles, publicistic works were found in newspapers and magazines of that time. He also says that he has many works. At the same time, he participated in the press with a number of articles. In the same year - 1999, under the editorship of Ozad Sharafiddinov, Elbek's poetry collection "Mungli Kushim" (Abdullayev O. 1999, p. 5) was published. The candidate of philology Ortiqboy Abdullayev prepared this bouquet, which started with the best poems of Elbek, who bravely fought for independence and was persecuted, for publication. Doctor, professor Ibrahim Yorkin writes a foreword to this book under the title "Nationalist poet of Turkestan Elbek". During the preface, he mentions that he has seen Elbek, attended school with him, and says that he is somewhat aware of his life: "I am a student of the new method (usuli jadid) elementary school opened by Eshonkhoja Khani in Tashkent, in the Lower Devonbegi neighborhood. When I was in the last grade, our poet came to Tashkent from his village, started attending classes in our class. Mashriq Elbek and I started attending the Rushdi section, which was opened in the school of Munavvar Gari near Sheikhontohur, after graduating from the elementary school of Eshankhoja Khani. He was about 4 years older than me. In 1919, he married the younger sister of the poet Mirmulla, writer Muslim and Mirmuhsin, and before I left Tashkent, he had a little son".

By 2017, another scientist Ulugmurad Amonov reprints the book Elbek's "Armug'on.Yolqinlar" ("Armugan.Yolkinlar"). It should be remembered that the "State Publishing House of the Republic of Turkestan" first published the poetry collections "Armug'an" and "Yalqinlar" in 1925. "Momaguldurak" and "Elbek. Selected Works", there are parables and poems that are not found in the books ("Kuchsizlar dunyosi", ("The World of the Weak"), "Sichqonlar kengashi" ("The Council of Mice"), "Maymunning qoziligi" ("The Monkey's Judgement"), "Jinning olov yoqishi" ("The Demon's Lighting of Fire"), "Chol bilan kampir" ("The Old

Man and the Old Woman”), “Qo‘ychi bilan bo‘ri” (“The Sheep and the Wolf”)) will be a witness.

The scientist continues to conduct scientific research and publish articles. In different years, together with Sh.R.Saparova, he publishes articles such as “Philologist, teacher, children's poet Elbek”, “Classification of Elbek’s poems in five directions”. In the article “Classification of Elbek’s poems in five directions”, the poems of our contemporary are classified in five directions: homeland, man, women’s freedom, love and nature. it is said that poetic scenes are expressed (Amanov U. Saparov Sh. 2021, p. 123).

In the article “Philologist, scientist, teacher, children’s poet Elbek” Elbek’s works such as “Yozuv yo‘llari” (“The ways of writing”), “Go‘zal yozg‘ichlar” (“Beautiful notebooks”), “Armug‘on” (“Armugan”) are highlighted (Amanov U. Saparov Sh. 2022, p. 363).

Such scientific researches, analyzes and press releases are continued by our scientists. After all, such works are important for an objective assessment of Elbek’s life and work.

In conclusion, it should be noted that Elbek is a light on the path of freedom. He not only created, made a great contribution to the development of children’s literature, but also considered the pain of the people as his own pain. He defined issues such as his freedom and development as his main goal. In accordance with his name, he appeared as the leader, captain, leader, and beg of the nation, calling the people to enlightenment, and spared nothing on the way. But, unfortunately, Elbek, like our other great-grandfathers, was not encouraged for these great works, on the contrary, he was accused as a “nationalist”, “counter-revolutionary”. He created while living in Turkestan's bosom, where white and red insects nested, and barbarism was rampant. Regardless of what happened, the immortal creation of our grandfathers will live forever in our hearts.

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